

TEMPERATURE EFFECTS ON SPUTTERED ITO

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ABSTRACT: Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) is widely used in solar cell devices for its excellent electrical and optical characteristics, such as high transparency in the Ultraviolet-Visible range and good conductivity (around $10^4 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$). In this work we have compared thin (70-150 nm) ITO layers deposited by Direct Current or Radio Frequency sputtering. We have used different substrate temperatures during film growth and have afterwards thermally annealed the samples at different temperatures up to 300°C to investigate the effects on the electrical and optical properties of the material. We have found out that the different growth/annealing conditions induce changes in the optical properties of the samples as well as in the conductivity and carrier concentration.

Keywords: ITO; annealing

1 INTRODUCTION

In heterojunction solar cells, a key point for achieving high efficiency is the deposition of a Transparent Conductive Oxide (TCO) layer as full-area contact on both base and emitter side of the solar cell. Various TCOs have been studied through the years as alternatives to Indium Tin Oxide (ITO), to circumvent its relative high cost and Indium shortage in nature. Aluminum Oxide, Tungsten Oxide and Cerium Oxide [1-3] have attracted interest in the recent past, but ITO still remains the most widely used as TCO in heterojunction (HJ) solar cells [4,5] manufacturing because of its excellent electrical and optical characteristics, such as high transparency in the ultraviolet-visible range and good conductivity, typically 80% and 10^4 S-cm^{-1} respectively for a thin film also useful as antireflection coating [6].

Among the available deposition techniques for ITO growth, the most efficient and widely used is Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD). Both Radio Frequency (RF) and Direct Current (DC) magnetron sputtering are suitable to obtain high-quality films for photovoltaic applications. The DC process is very simple and easy to be scaled up on large area, with relatively high growth rates. In turn, the RF process requires the use of a matching network between the power generator and the target, and results in lower deposition rates. If this latter could be a drawback for scalability, it could represent an advantage because of the lower ion bombardment, which, in principle, should reduce stress on the underlying films. In this work we have studied the intrinsic properties of ITO for Photovoltaic applications in silicon heterojunction solar cells [7], where thin films are used to work also as antireflection coating. In particular, we have grown thin (<150 nm) ITO films by in-line, large area DC and RF magnetron sputtering, at different power densities and substrate temperatures. The samples have been subsequently thermally annealed up to 300°C to explore the effects of temperature during and after deposition. The results obtained on DC- and RF-grown samples have been compared and discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

ITO samples have been deposited on Corning glass in an in-line, large area deposition system by DC Magnetron Sputtering at a constant pressure of 1.1×10^{-3} mbar in Argon (Ar) without Oxygen addition. The target was an Indium-Tin alloy with a 90%:10% In:Sn weight ratio and

170 cm^2 area. The power has been fixed at 200 W and the substrate temperature during deposition has been varied between Room Temperature (RT) and 180°C. Similar samples have been grown by 13.56 MHz RF sputtering from a 6 inches diameter round target of same ITO alloy at 100W power and 3.3×10^{-3} mbar pressure, at various substrate temperatures between RT and 180°C.

The samples have been characterized in terms of Reflectance (R) and Transmittance (T) by a Perkin Elmer Lambda 950 UltraViolet-Visible-NearInfrared (UV-Vis-NIR) spectro-photometer. Bulk film resistivity has been evaluated by measuring the sheet Resistance (R_{sh}) with a Four Point Probe tool and thickness by a Tencor Alphastep contact profilometer. After deposition, the samples have been thermally annealed in a static IR furnace under Nitrogen flux for 10 minutes at different temperatures from 100°C to 300°C, and again characterized. The samples have been also characterized in terms of mobility (μ), free carrier density (N) and resistivity (ρ) in a Biorad Hall profiler according to the Van der Paw configuration.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have started by characterizing the DC-grown samples. Figure 1 shows the absorption coefficient before and after thermal treatment. The as-dep samples show noticeable differences, and the higher the deposition temperature, the lower the absorption. After a thermal treatment, the absorption decreases for all samples in the UV-Vis range.

In Fig. 2 we report the effects on bulk resistivity (ρ) of thermal annealing performed in several temperature steps on the same samples reported in Fig. 1. All samples show a step-like decreasing trend of ρ with increasing annealing temperature, and the lower the deposition temperature, the higher the resistivity. The transition temperatures for the three samples, defined as the temperature at which the slope of the curves in Fig. 2 is maximum and the ITO films change drastically their characteristics, are very different for the three samples,

and decrease from about 195°C for the samples grown at RT to 160°C and 155°C for the samples grown at higher temperatures. The ρ values after thermal annealing at 250°C become comparable for all the ITO films grown at different temperatures.

Figure 1: Absorption coefficient before (solid line) and after (dashed line) thermal annealing at 300°C in samples grown at different substrate temperatures and 200 W. Different color intensities refer to different deposition temperatures

Figure 2: Resistivity as a function of thermal annealing temperature in samples grown at 200W and different substrate temperatures. Lines are only a guide for the eye.

On the basis of the previous observations, we have selected two deposition conditions, i.e. 200 W power and RT and 180°C substrate temperature, to be compared with two analogous of samples deposited by RF sputtering. The samples have been thermally annealed at different temperatures and optically characterized in terms of Reflectance and Transmittance in a range extended to 1200 nm, so as to cover the one of interest for crystalline silicon based heterojunction solar cells. Electrical characterizations have been carried out by Hall measurements

Figure 3 shows the absorption coefficient of the samples grown at RT and 180°C by both DC and RF process. It is evident that the DC samples are less transparent than the RF ones in the whole spectral range. For DC samples, a thermal annealing at 180°C induces only small changes on α , because the transition temperature has not been reached yet. On the other hand, growing the sample directly at 180°C leads to a higher improvement of transparency in the 400-650 nm range.

Concerning the RF samples, their absorption coefficients are much lower than those of the DC samples, and the higher the deposition temperature, the better the transparency in the 400-1200 nm range. Samples grown at RT show a slight increase in transparency after a thermal annealing at 180°C.

Figure 3: Absorption coefficient in the UV-Vis-NIR spectral range for samples grown by DC and RF sputtering at different temperatures.

Table I summarizes the extinction coefficients of the samples in the Vis-NIR range, calculated from the α values, clearly showing the higher transparency of the RF-grown samples.

Electrical characterizations have been performed on the samples in terms of mobility (μ), free carrier density (N) and resistivity (ρ), and the results are reported in Fig. 4. From Fig. 4 (top) it is seen that the resistivity of the as-dep RF samples (around $4 \times 10^{-4} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$) is less influenced by the deposition temperature with respect to that of DC samples, which varies from 1.2×10^{-4} to $0.4 \times 10^{-4} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ for RT and 180°C deposition, respectively. In both RF samples ρ is lower than that of the RT grown DC sample, but comparable to that of the DC sample deposited at 180°C. The effect of thermal annealing on resistivity is quite different for the 4 sets of samples. While for both DC samples a step-function decrease is observed, confirming what shown in Fig. 4, the RF samples show different behaviors depending on the deposition temperature. Indeed, for ITO deposited at 180°C (RF2), a small increment with thermal annealing temperature is recorded. On the other hand, for the films deposited by RF power at RT (RF1) a considerable increase is observed.

TABLE I: Vis-NIR extinction coefficients of DC and RF samples grown at different temperatures

Sample	633 nm	1000 nm
DC RT	0.06	0.09
DC 180°C	0.05	0.16
RF RT	0.01	0.03
RF 180°C	0.005	0.03

The free carrier density variation after thermal treatment are also shown in Fig. 4. The N trends can be directly correlated to those of ρ values. Indeed the relative differences in N values of the DC samples before thermal annealing reflect those of ρ , with values of $1.6 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the DC sample grown at RT, and lower

but similar values (around $6.5 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) for the DC sample grown at 180°C and for both the RF samples. After annealing, the N values for the DC samples have raised up to over $2.2 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, while the RF samples show a much lower variability.

Figure 4: From top to bottom: resistivity, carriers concentration and mobility as a function of annealing temperature for samples grown at different substrate temperatures, by both DC and RF sputtering. Lines are only a guide for the eye.

For what concerns mobility, in the bottom of Fig. 4, it is immediate to note that just after deposition the RF samples are characterized by a higher mobility ($26.6 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V s}$) with respect to the one of the DC samples ($10 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V s}$). The mobilities of RF and DC samples show a decreasing and increasing trend, respectively, with increasing annealing temperature, with a convergence of the values for all samples around $16 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V s}$.

The coupled analysis of N and μ can explain the resistivity variations reported in Fig. 4. For the DC samples, the global increase of both N and μ with increasing annealing temperature results in a corresponding decrease of ρ . For the RF sample grown at RT, the annealing causes a decrease in both μ and N, with an enhancement of resistivity, especially at 300°C . In the RF sample grown at 180°C a compensation between the increase in N and the decrease in μ with

increasing annealing temperature does not produce large variations in the film resistivity.

Summing up all these considerations, it can be established that the RF technique is able to produce ITO films having lower resistivity, higher mobility and lower carrier concentration with respect to the DC samples grown at RT. DC samples grown at 180°C are comparable to RF samples in terms of electrical parameters, even if their transparency remains lower. However the resistivity of films deposited by RF can be negatively affected by a thermal treatment, especially when carried out at temperatures above 180°C .

Layers deposited via DC sputtering can suffer from very high free carrier absorption, affecting the transparency in the NIR part of the spectrum, especially when deposited at 180°C , due to N concentrations in the order of 10^{21} cm^{-3} . Thermal treatments further increase this concentration as well as the mobility, which corresponds to an improvement in transport properties. The illustrated different electro-optical properties of ITO films grown by DC or RF techniques can be exploited when designing the cells manufacturing process sequence, by choosing between the different deposition conditions depending on the properties to be privileged, i.e. transparency or conductivity, and on the thermal process the device has to undergo.

Figure 5: Internal Quantum Efficiencies of complete cells th different top ITO layers, before and after annealing.

To better asses the performances of ITO films, they have been used as top window layers in complete solar cells which were produced in parallel and differentiated only for the ITO layer. The cells structure starts from n-type c-Si wafer passivated on both sides by a buffer layer of intrinsic hydrogenated amorphous silicon (i-a-Si:H). The back contact is constituted by a layer of n-type amorphous hydrogenated Silicon Oxide (n-SiO_x:H) covered by Al-doped Zinc Oxide (AZO). The front side is completed by a p-type a-Si:H layer finally covered by the different ITO layers. Ag evaporated grids complete the cell on both sides as electrodes.

For this comparison, we have focused on ITO films deposited at RT for both DC and RF sputtering, and we have subsequently annealed the cells at 180°C . Since the different ITOs should only affect optical and electrical properties of the cells in terms of J_{sc} collection, we have measured the cells Quantum Efficiencies and Reflectances, and we have computed the Internal Quantum Efficiencies (IQE). The results are reported in

Fig. 5. As expected, the cell containing ITO grown by RF sputtering is the best performing one in the measured range, with a further slight improvement after thermal annealing. On the contrary, the cell containing the DC grown ITO layer shows much lower response, increasing after thermal treatment. This latter behavior is the consequence of enhanced transparency and conductivity of DC ITO after thermal annealing as already shown in Fig. 4.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have shown the effect of temperature on DC and RF sputtered ITO thin films. We have considered both substrate heating during the deposition and subsequent thermal treatments, finding out that in all cases higher temperatures lead to better results in terms of transparency.

For DC sputtered ITO, mobility has been found to be slightly dependent on substrate deposition temperature and subsequent thermal treatments. The free carrier concentration has resulted higher for samples deposited at 180°C, with an increase after thermal annealing for both deposition temperatures. These effects are reflected on the absorption coefficient, which is lower in the IR part of the spectrum for samples deposited at higher temperatures.

The RF sputtering technique produces ITO film with better characteristics just after deposition with respect to samples grown by DC sputtering at RT. In particular, the absorption coefficient is lowered by almost one order of magnitude in the 450-1200 nm range, while the resistivity is less than one half. Nevertheless the conductivity of these films is worsened by post-deposition thermal treatments, especially when performed at temperatures above 180°C.

The different temperature responses of DC and RF sputtered ITO layers have been verified at cell level by means of IQE measurements.

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